

Deliverable JRP2 – 2.1:

A questionnaire has been completed by all partners to assess the criteria for inclusion of retrospective and prospective studies.

Retrospective study

The tables below summarises the response from each veterinary partner and indicates the types of samples that are present in their archives.

	Poultry	Pigs	Veal/cattle
NVI	X		
UCM	X	X	
APHA		X	
ANSES			X
WBVR	X	X	X

For medical colleagues the retrospective collection are varied.

Both the animal and human isolates to be used from retrospective studies the criteria is still under discussion and will be finalized when data from all the strain collections become available.

Prospective study

The samples that each veterinary partner intends to collect from prospective studies:

	Poultry	Pigs	Veal
NVI		X	
UCM		X	
APHA		X	
UoS	X	X	
ANSES			X
WBVR	X		X

There are no criteria for the animal isolates and we will attempt to harmonise methods as much as possible across partners.

For the prospective studies for the human isolates the criteria is that the first 20 *Escherichia coli* isolated from urine from each hospital at each month over a year will be included.